

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF CARGO TERMINAL ACTIVITY CRITERIA

Shoira Khoshimova Safarovna

Teacher of Transport Logistics Department

Jizzakh Polytechnics Institute

E-mail address: shoira.xoshimova@mail.ru

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8285816>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th August 2023

Accepted: 25th August 2023

Online: 26th August 2023

KEY WORDS

Transport-logistics, cargo terminal, transportation, indicators, expenses.

ABSTRACT

The article states that the timely delivery of goods and the satisfaction of customer needs directly depend on the efficient operation of cargo terminals. In this, the technological process stages of transportation through the terminal and the criteria of effective management of the activity of the terminal transportation system were formed, and the priority of terminal transportation over direct transportation was established.

In order to ensure the innovative development of the economy, there is a need to establish a "transport-logistics" system in the country. Today, the share of the transport network in the gross domestic product of our country is 11 percent. This shows how important the system is, that is, it is an infrastructural area that has a high impact on the development of other areas. Stable and effective operation of the "transport-logistics" system, further development of various branches of industry and agriculture in the regions, is a necessary condition for improving the living standards and conditions of the country's population.[1]

It is an important issue for our developing country to organize an effective system of cargo delivery. By efficient timely delivery of goods, first of all, consistency of movement of finished products and raw materials in the domestic market and reduction of prices of products delivered to consumers is achieved.

In Uzbekistan, there is a need to create universal logistics terminals that can provide a full range of logistics services related to transportation, processing, storage and retail sales. In this regard, the development of logistics terminals to increase the volume of export of goods and transport services, to optimize imports and to attract additional flows of transit cargo is considered to be an important task.[2]

It is worth noting that measures are being taken to ensure the rapid and balanced development of the regions in exchange for using the new possibilities of the development of the "Logistics Terminal" system and rationally using the potential of the "Logistics Terminal". At the same time, great importance is attached to the modernization of the "logistics-terminal" system in our country, providing them with the most modern, advanced equipment and technologies, creating and implementing new developments in the fields of science and technology. At the same time, in the organization of transport-logistics services, a

number of scientific and research works dedicated to the optimization of the transportation of goods in the national economy were carried out in order to effectively provide the needs of consumers for transportation volumes, reduce transportation costs, and increase the work efficiency of motor vehicles.

Major researchers, D.Dzh. Bauersox, Velmozhin A.V., Gudkov V.A., Mirotin L.B., with issues such as organization of transport and logistics services in production processes, optimization of economic management and reduction of material costs. , V.S. Lukinskyi, S.M. Mochalin, Sh.A. Butaev. G.A. Samatov, M.N. It is covered in detail in the scientific works of Juraev et al.

Effective organization of transport and logistics services is manifested in transportation in terminal systems, where the integration of a large number of logistics tasks is formed. Specialization of cargo terminals allows to increase the quality of customer service and reduce logistics costs[3]

In today's conditions, high-level transport-logistics demands are placed by customers on the quality of transport services, transportation process and results.

In the efficient organization of transport and logistics services, it is important to plan logistics operations based on the coordinated and efficient operation of fast information and technical and technological means, and to manage the supply chain.[4]

In recent years, the integrated logistics system has been used to effectively manage the "design - procurement - production - distribution - sales - service" flows. In this, it is to combine different functional areas and their participants within a single logistics system. The effective operation of logistics transport and distribution systems is aimed at the management of material and relevant information and financial flows based on a systematic approach, as well as optimization of planning and coordination of the economic interests of all participants of the logistics system.

Cargo terminals are one of the main objects of logistics infrastructure. A cargo terminal is a special complex of structures, personnel, technical and technological devices that are organizationally interconnected and designed to perform logistics operations related to the reception, loading and unloading, storage, sorting, and processing of various batches of goods. The terminal is the initial, final part of the transport network. and is a complex of devices located at intermediate points. Terminals ensure the interaction of various types of transport in the process of transporting cargo. The technological process of transportation through the terminal consists of three main stages:

1. delivery of goods to the terminal;
2. cargo handling at the terminal;
3. Shipment of goods and linear transportation to designated places.

Linear (highway) transportation between terminals can be carried out in different types of transport and according to different schemes. Loading at the terminal, as a rule, is carried out in the evening, and the movement of the road train is carried out at night to reach the point (terminal) in the morning. The quality of terminal transport is characterized by high speed of cargo delivery and efficient use of vehicles. If the warehouse enterprises perform the task of storing goods, in addition to the collection of goods at the terminals, they perform the

main functions related to the distribution and consolidation, the formation and distribution of goods along the transportation routes.

A modern cargo terminal is an enterprise engaged in various types of activities, including cargo transportation, storage and sale of many additional services, such terminal complexes include:

- special warehouses for storage and processing of goods;
- container terminals and vehicle storage platforms;
- buildings for the performance of customs functions by relevant services;
- bank branches and certification centers;
- forwarding and brokerage firms;
- insurance companies;
- wholesale and retail trade centers and business centers;
- trade of clients, including foreign firms administrative buildings and offices of representative offices;
- security services;
- computing and information-logistics centers;
- vehicle maintenance centers;
- wholesale and retail stores and showrooms;
- analytical research centers.

In addition, due to the equipment of terminal complexes with modern equipment and software, the process of sorting goods will be accelerated, which will allow processing of very large volumes of incoming goods. In addition, the process of automatic movement of goods of different groups. in case of any unexpected situations, it also allows to adjust the delivery route correctly based on considerations of shortening the path and ensuring the maximum possible safety of the goods.

The technological cycle of cargo terminals consists of the following three processes: import, export and transit.

The first process, import, involves unloading, warehousing, and delivering the cargo to the customer. The second process involves providing transportation services for export shippers, receiving cargo at the warehouse, delivering from the warehouse, and loading. The third process, transit, is a combination of the first two processes, often with intermediate operations added.

Along with the main technological processes, the following auxiliary processes are performed in cargo terminals:

- making schedules for all stages of the technological cycle and monitoring them;
- providing various services to customers, calculating and monitoring payments;
- coordinating branch warehouse activities;
- monitoring of the cargo during transportation and checking the state of marking;
- implementation of customs control in temporary storage warehouses.

Modern terminals make it possible to use information technologies and automated systems of operations, reduce the time of cargo transportation and improve its quality. This is achieved by controlling the execution of the technological cycle, reducing losses and damage during the transportation of goods, and increasing income depends on the following factors:

- increasing cargo turnover by reducing cargo transportation time;
- attract new customers and carriers by improving the quality of services;
- to improve the quality of decisions made by obtaining complete and timely information[6].

Also, it will be possible to effectively manage the activity of the terminal transport system in the following directions:

1. Modern terminals allow the use of information technologies and automated systems of activity, reduce the time of cargo transportation and improve its quality. This is achieved by controlling the execution of the technological cycle, reducing losses and damage during the transportation of goods.

2. Implementation of small batch shipments of various shippers using the logistics scheme, the reduction of transportation costs is achieved. In this case, cargo transportation requires different conditions and the selection of appropriate vehicles.

3. By optimizing the work of intermediate links of the cargo supply chain, it is possible to increase the efficiency of the activity

4. The technological nature of the need for the transport volume of terminal addresses and consumer addresses, the satisfaction of this need, full of opportunities for sending (receiving) cargo usage and transportation costs are ensured to be minimal in accordance with the selected criteria.

5. It is necessary to determine the characteristics of the conditions that lead to random fluctuations in the values of various transport indicators characterizing the elementary processes of transportation in the terminal system, to determine the basic elementary processes and to form appropriate mathematical models for them. Such basic elementary processes are different for different routes (j), vehicles (i), loads (l) and destinations (n) in freight transport processes. The activity of vehicles of type i operating on route j is formed by the following constant q_n , g_{st} , $lyukl$, lux and random t_{j-k} , $B_{юкл}$, $B_{юкс}$ character indicators

6. Organization of modern terminal activities on the basis of cluster principles is the basis for increasing the volume and types of services, increasing the innovativeness of transport services and reducing service costs [6-15]. Currently, clusters are the most modern means of system development in regions. The advantages of the cluster approach are that it allows enterprises in the terminal system to take a comprehensive, systematic review of the situation and use them effectively.

Transportation is carried out in two ways, and in terminal transportation of goods, along with delivery, unloading, sorting, storage and loading of goods, customs clearance is carried out at the terminal. In direct transportation, customs clearance of goods (detention in temporary storage warehouses at customs) is carried out with the participation of senders and receivers. In this case, the terminal transport efficiency condition is expressed as follows: $T \leq P$; here, T is transportation costs at the terminal; P is the cost of direct transportation.

Assuming that these costs are the same for both options (except for customs clearance costs), they are determined as follows: In terminal transportation: $T_R = T + T_x = (S_1 + R_1 + S_2 + X + R_2) + T_x$; here:

T - terminal costs;

T_x - international inter-terminal transportation costs;

S_1 - delivery of cargo in a vehicle of low load capacity

expenses;

R_1 - unloading costs at the terminal;

S_2 - cargo sorting costs at the terminal;

X - the price of cargo storage at the terminal;

R_2 - loading costs at the terminal.

As can be seen from above, cargo storage is mainly provided in terminal transportation and full loading of motor vehicles in international transportation [16-30]. Therefore, the efficiency of transportation at the terminal is highly valued. Thus, effective operation of transport systems in international transportation, timely delivery of goods and satisfaction of customers' needs directly depends on the organization of efficient operation of cargo terminals.

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